

IMPORTANT LEGAL DOCUMENT ON SUPPORT AND PROMOTION OF LEGAL EDUCATION (Uzbekistan context)

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ABSTRACT

In subsequent integration processes, any area in the society should remain and continue to function even after the pandemic. This is also relevant in the higher education system. The announcement of the pandemic led to the introduction of remote organization of the educational process and the creation of online classes. At the same time, the adoption by the President of a decree on the fundamental improvement of legal education and science in the Republic of Uzbekistan increased attention to education in these processes. The article discusses the significance of the decree and answers to the questions arisen in this area.

Introduction

The development of any legal state is directly related to the composition and quality of highly qualified legal personnel that meet international standards. The training of highly qualified legal personnel is a specific and complex process. After all, legal personnel play an important role in the legal support of the ongoing reforms in our country, in creating its legal framework. Therefore, the adoption of a decree by the President of our state "On additional measures to radically improve legal education and science in the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated April 29, 2020, which literally marked the beginning of a new period of improving the system of legal training in our country, is the same fact. [1]

We must recognize that over the past years, many systemic problems have accumulated in the field of legal education. The location of the University of Law in the center prevented the emergence of healthy competition in this regard. It also limited the opportunity for equal education for our young people living in different regions who set out to become lawyers. Also, despite the fact that scientific research is led in various areas of law, the application of their results in practice is not at the level of demand, insufficient attention is paid to the modification of educational programs in connection with modern requirements, which has led to a reduction in the quality of legal education and scientific potential. [2] Improving the quality of the

educational process is the most important life criterion. The road map approved by the decree sets important tasks for preparing the educational process based on modern requirements and international standards. In particular, it provided for the organization of training of students on the basis of modern forms and methods of teaching, pedagogical, information and communication, innovative technologies that will ensure the formation of analytical thinking, independent acquisition and use of new knowledge, skills and abilities. Based on the experience of the most advanced foreign countries and the practice of higher educational institutions that occupy prestigious places in the international ranking, educational plans and programs are being revised again. They will focus the main attention of students on their professional activities. At the same time, in order to fully digitize the educational process, it is planned to introduce the project "Electronic University". It will carry out a large-scale work on accepting written works of students, encrypting them, verifying, evaluating and summarizing the results, translating information about lesson tables, the activities of students and the teaching staff into a full electronic form. At the same time, the European credit Transfer and Accumulation System (Accumulation System ECTS) is being introduced, which is practiced in most prestigious foreign universities. A positive aspect of this system is that the student's mastering of each subject is carried out by collecting a certain number of credits (points), as well as creating a wide range of amenities when transferring a student to study from one University to another. Thanks to this, state educational standards, educational plans

and scientific programs are reviewed in accordance with the credit system. The necessary conditions are being created for the preparation of new textbooks and teaching AIDS, as well as the translation of textbooks prepared at universities in foreign countries.

Methodology

On the basis of advanced foreign experience in law, a co-working center for practice-oriented classes will be created, as well as a Legal Tech laboratory for the development and implementation of new information and communication technologies. What changes are expected in the digitization of legal education in Uzbekistan? Today, the education system is determined not only by international competition, but also by national competitiveness, primarily by how much it corresponds to the demand of that period. Therefore, according to this decree, a number of innovations in the legal field in the direction of scientific research and innovation are expected. The first innovation, without digitizing modern education, is to make it quickly adaptable to a diverse environment. In particular, we feel the need to make the educational process electronic and introduce these technologies in it in the context of a pandemic. [3] The decree has defined the task of transition to a full-fledged electronic document management, digitization of research and educational process at the University. It should be noted that e-University projects in developed foreign countries have been considered an effective program for many years. What does the E-University project provide and what are its advantages? First of all, the full implementation of this project at the University creates an

opportunity not only in the field of scientific research, but also to fully automate the educational process. For this purpose, you can list such opportunities as forming the content of classes, conducting exams, certifications, forming student ratings, creating distance learning classes, planning scientific events, conducting online discussions on dissertations. In addition, the implementation of the e-University system serves to create an open, transparent educational environment, free from subjectivism and abuse. In short, corruption is considered an important element in creating an educational environment. It turns out that this task will also fully comply with the state program of "Year of development of science, education and the digital economy" by 2020. The second innovation – the decree establishes the task of creating and establishing a Legal Tech laboratory for the purpose of developing and implementing new information technologies and systems in the country. Technology of Legal Tech is a completely new system for Uzbekistan and provides scientific and innovative research in the field of state and law of Uzbekistan.

Let's briefly talk about what this technology is and its significance in the legal field. In our time, information technology has begun to penetrate into any field of activity. It is worth noting that in the legal practice of developed foreign countries, as above, information technology programs are used quite productively. Such legal technology is called a legal technique. For example, a team at the American Institute of technology in Illinois developed a program aimed at predicting how the US Supreme court will decide on a legal dispute. Usually, 70 percent of an analytical forecast is

correct. Similar programs are being created in Canada. An example of this is a special online application aimed at ensuring that a person who has violated the traffic rules and is dissatisfied with the fine imposed by the police for this, can go to court without the help of a lawyer, as well as ensure that his case is considered in a short time.

We can also highlight such programs as legal disputes, search for legal norms that will apply to problems, and contract review. Such legal technologies are created in the Legal Tech. This will also require joint work of lawyers and experts in the field of export technologies. The creation and implementation of Legal Tech programs in Uzbekistan in the conditions of a shortage of lawyers, including lawyers, will allow in the future to increase the ability of lawyers to provide legal services to a large number of citizens using legal technology with short opportunities. What tasks have been identified to improve the national and international ranking of Tashkent State University of Law? The goal is to improve the position of the University in the National ranking, as well as to include it in the list of the best higher educational institutions in the ratings of internationally recognized organizations until 2030, the task is to develop and approve a comprehensive action plan.

Results

Tashkent State University of Law has identified important short- and long-term goals in this direction. Based on these tasks of the Head of our state, it is possible to once again improve our areas of activity. It should be noted that higher education institutions that occupy the first 1000 places in the ranking of internationally

Quacquarelli recognized organizations (Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings, Times Higher Education or Academic Ranking of World Unique universities) are considered internationally recognized higher education institutions.[1] The above measures are aimed at attracting foreign investment to our University, increase the chances of foreign students, improving the efficiency and international recognition of educational programs, improvement of research results of professors and teachers in international scientific databases (Scopus, Web of Science , etc.), in short the University is to increase the international ranking. As a logical continuation of this task, the decree also establishes the task of providing access to international databases in the field of law (LexisNexis, WestLaw, JStore, etc.). This, in turn, creates an opportunity not only for professors and lecturers of the University, but also for representatives of the entire legal science to get acquainted with the latest achievements of international legal science.

Discussion

In addition, according to the resolution, "TSUL Legal Report" is defined the task of implementing the law journal of students who are successfully being reviewed and organizing its systematic publication in paper and electronic form. This question is extremely relevant. The reason was that until that day, there was no special journal for students to publish their research in. This, in turn, will serve to ensure the continuity of talented students with research activities, and integration into science. Consistent implementation of training of specialists with modern knowledge and excellent skills in the life of

society requires the implementation of both large-scale and deep reforms in the national education system. Currently, the fact that the teaching staff of TSUL conducts teaching remotely via the Internet based on video and audio lessons, e-books, educational materials, serves to increase the effectiveness of national education systems. This, in turn, is a result of the high level of development of information and communication technologies in TSUL. Our President noted that serious changes in the education sector are expected in the near future due to the digitization process. Electronic (digital) education is a learning system based on information and electronic technologies. Personal mastering of electronic educational materials using information and communication technologies, receiving consultations from distance teachers, evaluating their knowledge, and so on are part of this type of education. [4] If we attach great importance to paragraph 1 of this Decree, it provides for the introduction of distance, correspondence and evening training programs for people with basic higher legal education on the job, which will serve to harmonize the knowledge of students working in practice with theory and to train high-quality personnel.[5] The order of distance learning in online mode (video lectures, consultations, and control types in real time) and offline (independent acquisition of relevant educational and methodological resources in the distance learning system) is justified. In distance education professors and teachers of higher educational institutions post educational materials to provide our citizens with an opportunity to remotely obtain secondary and higher education on all specialties and professions, including

using the electronic education system of foreign universities, e-books, manuals, special interactive programs, videos, the creation of special government institutions to accelerate the development and certification of the literature and comprehensive support to its activities is a high demand. While there are currently about 4,000 consultants in Uzbekistan, the development of civil society requires an increase in the number of professional consultants. Currently, if a professor works in a permanent staff and works in a law firm, then there will definitely be his track record, and the main place of work will be the law firm. However, some professors want to work in several places that are in harmony with the practice and theory of teachers. This situation prevents teachers from practicing the law. If you look at the experience of some foreign countries, then in these countries a professor may not only work as a full-time teacher, but also can be engaged in the activities of a lawyer. This makes it possible to raise the education

system to a qualitatively new level. Consequently, it makes it possible to train modern specialists with high civil and professional potential. Taking into account the legal reforms carried out in the category of textbooks and teaching aids of the new generation, training of personnel with the involvement of foreign scientists and specialists is carried out gradually. There is also a need to create an opportunity to use electronic textbooks, training manuals, special interactive programs, video materials created by the world's leading educational institutions in the process of obtaining distance education. In conclusion, it should be noted that in order to save state budget funds by eliminating regional and temporary barriers to education, one of the most urgent tasks is to organize in-depth study of Legal Sciences with a wide involvement in the distance learning process of qualified professors from prestigious higher educational institutions abroad.

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